

Required Employment Skills in Management Students, to get the Job Opportunity after their Academic Journey

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Abstract:- For a student to get the job after the finishing of the study, it is very difficult to understand the requirements of employer. In current competitive scenario management students are facing many types of difficulties to get their job. Employers are facing difficulties to find the right talent in students and students are not able to understand what type of skills employer is looking for. This is the primary responsibility of every institution to provide updated knowledge, different types of skills and professional behavior to their students so, that they can get the job easily. Institution should be aware about the job market competition and employer expectations. Their curriculums for students should be updated after every two years. If need of market will match with the management students ability, this is possible to get the right job for students. In this paper researcher will discuss about the different type of employability skill which is required to get a job, and what type of skills employer are expecting from their employees.

Keywords:- Employability Skill, Students, Ability, Curriculums, Primary responsibilities, Institution.

I. INTRODUCTION

As we all know employability skill is a set of skills & behavior. To get a job opportunity it is an important to develop these skills in students. The combinations of soft skills, foundational skills work- willingness skills or job willingness skill are called employability skills. These skills allow communicating with coworkers, problem solving ability, make responsible choices and take responsibility of your own career. With the help of personal qualities, habits and attitudes of how to interact with others can develop. In every organization employers value employability skills because, with the help of this they can linked to job performance & requirements, and career success etc. Essential employability skills to get a job are foundational skills, interpersonal skills, communication skills, problem solving and critical thinking, team work, apart from this other professional skills like career development, leadership etc.

With the help of foundational skills students can learn to be organized, be punctual, be loyal, be dependable, positive attitude toward work, complete task on time with accuracy, exert high level of efforts and determination, adaptability to change, seek out information to improve skills, understand dress code or uniform guidelines, maintain personal hygiene etc.

Interpersonal skills can help to develop friendly and polite nature, respect supervisors and coworkers, respect supervisors and coworkers, respond appropriately to customer requests, ask for feedback and resolve conflicts calmly and properly.

Another skill is communication skill which can help to follow the directions, read & understand written materials, listen and ask questions, express ideas clearly when speaking or writing and last one is learn required technology & use properly.

Problem solving and critical thinking skill can develop the acceptance capability of change, willing to start, stop & switch duties, start task without prompting, ask questions to solve problems for better job performance and work calmly in busy environment.

With the help of team work skill students can develop the capability of contribution to team goals. They can be sensitive to other people needs, comfortable working with people of different backgrounds, take accountability for own share of work etc.

Ethics & legal responsibilities skills can develop honesty and trustworthy ability, develop the ability of understanding and follow company rules and procedures, take responsibility for own decisions & actions, act professionally with maturity.

Other professional skills are very important to learn for students.

Career development is one of professional skill which can develop the ability to learn new skills and take different projects, understand industry and common business practices, align work goal with vision and mission of company, understand the various role of coworkers, take initiative and work with little supervision.

With the help of leadership skills development of negotiation skills can increase, willing to take risk, coach and mentor to others, save time and money for company by analyzing business requirements, build partnership and teams with coworkers, demonstrate efficiency etc.

II. LITERATURE OF REVIEW

- **Usimasamudrikawaligamage (2009)**, Sub Theme A- Enhancing Employability through Quality Assurance- ASAIHL 2009. This study was conducted with the objective of identifying the employer skills needs, for different countries. Researcher suggested various definitions related to employability skills, previous completed research in different countries related to the required employability skills. Researcher advised many things to enhance employability skills like universities should identify skill sets that will provide best future labor market.
- **NuryakeFajaryati, Budiyo, Muhammad Akhyar and wiranto, (2020)**, The Employability skills need to face the Demand of Work in the Future: Systematic Literature Reviews. In this study researcher aims to identify the employability skills needed in career field. In study analysis show employability skills are needed in relation to the work demand. To fight with global competition and future world work, individual need to improve their employability skills. Employer expectations are communication, team working, problem solving and technological skills from their employees.
- **P. Vanitha, Dr. A.T. Jaganatham**, A study on Enhancing Employability skills of Graduates in India. Suggested that in Indian college students are from different academic backgrounds coming from different place having different mother tongues so it is important to provide a common platform to make them enough competent. Employers are looking for different perceptions and expectations towards graduates skills like positive attitude, effective communication, problem solving, time management, team spirit, self-confidence etc.
- **Dr. M Nishad Nawaz, Dr. Bal Krishna (2013)**. Role of employability skills in Management education: A review. Suggested that all MBA graduates have to learn how to migrate from their comfort zone and go a long way towards impressing the boss of a new venture or a large multinational. Researchers realize that there is a huge gap between industry needs and available skills in students. Study was conducted with the objective of exploring the employability skills required for management graduates.
- **Dr. KavitaDesaia, JyotirmayeeRamisettyb, Dr. NiloferHussainic, Dr. MacherlaBhagyalakshmi (2021)**. Employability Skills Training Intervention in Higher Education in India: A Model Based Study. Researchers discussed about the employability skills- gap and job readiness of management students. The outcome of this study was all about skills development programs balance among academic skills, technical skills and employability skills.

III. SCOPE OF STUDY

The research study is limited to education sector and corporate sector. The scope of study is to recognize skills of students to get employment after their study.

IV. OBJECTIVES

- To find out the required skills of students for employment.
- To know about the employer’s expectations from employees.

V. PARAMETER OF STUDY

- Required skills to get job opportunity for management students.
- Employer’s expectations from management students as an employee.

Research Design- research is based on primary as well as secondary data. Primary data collected through survey method by filling questionnaires and interview methods of students and employer by over phone call interaction due to covid pandemic.

Statistical tool – Tool & technique selection play an important role in research. Data will be calculated through different statistical tools. In this research for strong representation, researcher will use figure and table.

VI. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

In this section of the report, descriptive statistics method has been applied. Basically, this method is used in the research to know about the nature of data set by help of computing mean, mode, median etc.

Gender		
Statistics		
Gender		
N	Valid	300
	Missing	0
Mean		1.73
Median		2.00
Mode		2
Std. Deviation		.445
Variance		.198
Skewness		-1.041
Std. Error of Skewness		.141
Kurtosis		-.922
Std. Error of Kurtosis		.281
Range		1
Minimum		1
Maximum		2
Sum		519

Table 1: Demographical information

Analysis- in accordance to the above table this can be seen that value of mean is 1.73 and median is 2.0. This shows that mean is lower than median which shows that data is not correctively skewed. In addition to this value of mean is too far from standard deviation ($2 > 0.445$). In addition to this, value of variance is 0.198 which indicates that there is lower degree of variation in the data set. It is so because of low value of variation that is under one ($1 < 0.198$).

Education qualification

Statistics		
Education qualification		
N	Valid	300
	Missing	0
Mean		2.67
Median		3.00
Mode		3
Std. Deviation		.661
Variance		.437
Skewness		.417
Std. Error of Skewness		.141
Kurtosis		-.656
Std. Error of Kurtosis		.281
Range		3
Minimum		1
Maximum		4
Sum		800

Table 2: Qualification information of students and employer

Analysis-Based on the above table, this can be seen that value of mean is 2.67 and median is 3.00 ($3 < 2.34$). It shows that data is not correctively skewed. In addition to this the value of standard deviation is 0.661 and mean is 2.67 ($2.67 > 0.661$). It indicates that the data set is not accurately distributed because of higher difference between standard deviation and mean. As well as to this variance value is 0.437 that is lower than one and it shows that there is lower degree of variation in the data set.

Current status

Statistics		
Current status		
N	Valid	300
	Missing	0
Mean		1.30
Median		1.00
Mode		1
Std. Deviation		.460
Variance		.212
Skewness		.860
Std. Error of Skewness		.141
Kurtosis		-1.269
Std. Error of Kurtosis		.281
Range		1
Minimum		1
Maximum		2
Sum		391

Table 3: Data distribution

Analysis- According to the above data, the mean is 1.30 and the median is 1.00 ($1.30 > 1.00$). It demonstrates that the data is properly skewed. Furthermore, the standard deviation is 0.460 and the mean is 1.30 ($1.30 > 0.460$). Because of the larger disparity between standard deviation and mean, it shows that the data set is not correctly distributed. In addition, the variance value is 0.212, which is less than one, indicating that the data set has a smaller degree of fluctuation.

VII. UNIVARIATE ANALYSIS

This is known as a form of analysis that is used to assess the data set by using one variable or factor (Kavitha, Varuna and Ramya, 2016). Under this, only single variable is used such as it can be used for frequency analysis of the data set. As per the available information about the data set, below frequency test has been done:

Gender

Gender					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Female	81	27.0	27.0	27.0
	male	219	73.0	73.0	100.0
	Total	300	100.0	100.0	

Table 4: Gender Based Information

Fig. 1: Gender Based Information

Analysis- as per the above table and chart, this can be seen that the sample size of study is 300. Among these respondents, the female are 81 and remaining are male which are 219. This shows that majority of candidates are male in this study.

Education qualification		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Doctorate	1	.3	.3	.3
	Graduate	129	43.0	43.0	43.3
	Postgraduate	139	46.3	46.3	89.7
	Undergraduate	31	10.3	10.3	100.0
Total		300	100.0	100.0	

Table 5: Educational details of students and employer

Fig. 2: Educational qualification details of students and employer.

Analysis- In accordance to the above table this can be seen that out of 300 respondents, there are only 1 respondent who has done the doctorate. Most of the respondents have done post graduate that has been justified by above table that shows hat around 139 respondents have done PG. In addition to this, 129 respondents have done graduation and 31 people have done under graduation.

H0 - There is a significant relationship between various types of employability skills and efficiency level of the management graduates.

H1: There is no significant relationship between various types of employability skills and efficiency level of the management graduates.

Test-In order to test this hypothesis, we have to find out the relation between both variables including types of employability skills and efficiency level. To assess the relation between two variables correlation analysis is one of the crucial technique. It is defined as method in which two variables are tested to find the relation to each other (Darlington and Hayes, 2017). In the case when value of Pearson correlation is under 0.3 than there has been poor relation. While if value is between 0.3 to 0.6 than there is average relation among variables and above 0.6 is considered as excellent relationship.

Questions taken for test: Question 1 and question 4

Correlations									
		1 Rank the employability skills, according to employers - [Communication skills]	1. Rank the employability skills, according to employers - [Time management skills]	1. Rank the employability skills, according to employers - [Teamwork]	1. Rank the employability skills, according to employers - [Problem-solving Skills]	1. Rank the employability skills, according to employers - [Organization and planning.]	1. Rank the employability skills, according to employers - [Self-management skills]	1. Rank the employability skills, according to employers - [Leadership skills]	4. Are employability factors helpful to enhance the efficiency and capabilities of the graduates at the workplace ?
1 Rank the employability skills, according to employers - [Communication skills]	Pearson Correlation	1	.906**	.960**	.926**	.823**	.861**	.901**	.677**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300
1. Rank the employability skills, according to employers - [Time management skills]	Pearson Correlation	.906**	1	.942**	.978**	.927**	.952**	.978**	.813**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300
1. Rank the employability skills, according to employers - [Teamwork]	Pearson Correlation	.960**	.942**	1	.969**	.884**	.901**	.938**	.731**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300
1. Rank the employability skills, according to employers - [Problem-solving Skills]	Pearson Correlation	.926**	.978**	.969**	1	.907**	.927**	.973**	.782**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300

1. Rank the employability skills, according to employers - [Organization and planning.]	Pearson Correlation	.823**	.927**	.884**	.907**	1	.983**	.922**	.893**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300
1. Rank the employability skills, according to employers - [Self-management skills]	Pearson Correlation	.861**	.952**	.901**	.927**	.983**	1	.947**	.879**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300
1. Rank the employability skills, according to employers - [Leadership skills]	Pearson Correlation	.901**	.978**	.938**	.973**	.922**	.947**	1	.857**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300
4. Are employability factors helpful to enhance the efficiency and capabilities of the graduates at the workplace?	Pearson Correlation	.677**	.813**	.731**	.782**	.893**	.879**	.857**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 6: Correlation between employability skills and efficiency level of the management graduates

The above table shows information about correlation between employability skills and efficiency level of the management graduates. Underneath detailed analysis of relation has been done:

Relation between communication skills and efficiency of graduates

As per the above table this can be seen that there has been excellent relation between communication skill and efficiency of graduates. This is so because value of Pearson correlation is above 0.6 that shows the positive relation between both variables.

Relation between time management skills and efficiency of graduates

As per the above table this can be seen that there has been excellent relation between time management skills and efficiency of graduates. This is so because value of Pearson correlation is .813 that is above 0.6 that shows the positive relation between both variables.

Relation between team work and efficiency of graduates

As per the above table this can be seen that there has been excellent relation between team work skills and efficiency of graduates. This is so because value of Pearson correlation is .731 that is above 0.6 that shows the positive relation between both variables.

Relation between problem solving skills and efficiency of graduates

As per the above table this can be seen that there has been excellent relation between problem solving skills and efficiency of graduates. This is so because value of Pearson correlation is .782 that is above 0.6 that shows the positive relation between both variables.

Relation between organization & planning skills and efficiency of graduates

According to the above data, there has been an outstanding relationship between problem solving skills and graduate efficiency. This is because the Pearson correlation coefficient is 0.893, which is more than 0.6, indicating a positive relationship between the two variables.

Relation between self-management skills and efficiency of graduates

According to the statistics shown above, there is a strong link between self-management skills and graduate efficiency. This is due to the Pearson correlation value being 0.879, which is greater than 0.6 and indicates a positive association between the two variables.

Relation between leadership skills and efficiency of graduates

According to the statistics shown above, there is a strong link between leadership skills and graduate efficiency. This is due to the Pearson correlation value being 0.857, which is greater than 0.6 and indicates a positive association between the two variables.

H0: The expectations of the employer depends on the employability skills for management Students

H1: The expectations of the employer does not depend on the employability skills for management Students

Test-In this hypothesis we have to check the dependency of one variable to another. To do so there are different tests that can be implemented as per the nature of data set. In the above case, linear regression model has been applied (Darlington and Hayes, 2016). This test is used to define the extent to which one variable depends on another.

Questions taken for test: Question one and question three have been taken for this test.

Model Summary									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.893a	.798	.793	.578	.798	165.049	7	292	.000
a. Predictors: (Constant), 1. Rank the employability skills, according to employers - [Leadership skills], 1 Rank the employability skills, according to employers - [Communication skills], 1. Rank the employability skills, according to employers - [Organization and planning.], 1. Rank the employability skills, according to employers - [Teamwork], 1. Rank the employability skills, according to employers - [Time management skills], 1. Rank the employability skills, according to employers - [Problem-solving Skills], 1. Rank the employability skills, according to employers - [Self-management skills]									
b. Dependent Variable: 3. According to you, which employability skills are expected by the employer more? [Critical thinking skills]									

Table 7: The higher degree of relation between both dependent and independent variables

Analysis- as per the above table this can be seen that value of R is 0.893 that shows the higher degree of relation between both dependent and independent variables. In addition to this the value of R square is 0.798 or 79.8% that indicates the total variation in the dependent variable (expectation of employers) can be explained by the independent variable (skills of employers)

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	386.183	7	55.169	165.049	.000 ^b
	Residual	97.604	292	.334		
	Total	483.787	299			
a. Dependent Variable: 3. According to you, which employability skills are expected by the employer more? [Critical thinking skills]						
b. Predictors: (Constant), 1. Rank the employability skills, according to employers - [Leadership skills], 1 Rank the employability skills, according to employers - [Communication skills], 1. Rank the employability skills, according to employers - [Organization and planning.], 1. Rank the employability skills, according to employers - [Teamwork], 1. Rank the employability skills, according to employers - [Time management skills], 1. Rank the employability skills, according to employers - [Problem-solving Skills], 1. Rank the employability skills, according to employers - [Self-management skills]						

Table 8: The expectations of the employer depend on the employability skills for management graduates

Analysis- Based on the above table this can be stated that the value of significance difference is 0.00 that is lower than 0.05. It indicates that there is null hypothesis which states that the expectations of the employer depend on the employability skills for management graduates.

Coefficients						
Model		Un standardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.048	.087		12.016	.000
	1. Rank the employability skills, according to employers - [Communication skills]	.577	.100	.599	5.749	.000
	1. Rank the employability skills, according to employers - [Time management skills]	-.633	.149	-.709	-4.255	.000
	1. Rank the employability skills, according to employers - [Teamwork]	.197	.142	.213	1.388	.166
	1. Rank the employability skills, according to employers - [Problem-solving Skills]	.120	.168	.133	.717	.474
	1. Rank the employability skills, according to employers - [Organization and planning.]	.073	.145	.080	.504	.615
	1. Rank the employability skills, according to employers - [Self-management skills]	.197	.179	.212	1.100	.272
	1. Rank the employability skills, according to employers - [Leadership skills]	.353	.134	.382	2.635	.009
a. Dependent Variable: 3. According to you, which employability skills are expected by the employer more? [Critical thinking skills]						

Table 9: Coefficients calculation of variable

Residuals Statistics					
	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Predicted Value	1.93	5.47	3.69	1.136	300
Residual	-.932	1.068	.000	.571	300
Std. Predicted Value	-1.550	1.562	.000	1.000	300
Std. Residual	-1.612	1.847	.000	.988	300
a. Dependent Variable: 3. According to you, which employability skills are expected by the employer more? [Critical thinking skills]					

Table 10: Information of data set distribution.

Analysis- as per the above table this can be seen that the data set is not appropriately distributed because value of mean and standard deviation has been far from each other.

Fig. 3: Dependent Variable: skills expected by employer.

H0: The new way to improve the skills depends on the way to improve the skills

H1: The new way to improve the skills does not depend on the way to improve the skills

Test-In this hypothesis testing, we are going to apply multiple linear regression approach to find the dependency of one variable to another. A variant of analysis in which the response variable has a linear connection with two independent variables is known as multiple regressions (Yarnold and Linden, 2016).

Between-Subjects Factors			
		Value Label	N
9. According to you, how graduates can improve their employability skills to overcome the challenges?	1	Build social media profile	16
	2	Completing regular education courses	32
	3	Participate in internship program	141
	4	Seek the trusted advice	25
	5	Sharpen up soft skills	60
	6	Take online courses	26

Table 11: Way to improve employability skills.

Multivariate Tests						
Effect		Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df	Sig.
Intercept	Pillai's Trace	.893	604.327b	4.000	291.000	.000
	Wilks' Lambda	.107	604.327b	4.000	291.000	.000
	Hotelling's Trace	8.307	604.327b	4.000	291.000	.000
	Roy's Largest Root	8.307	604.327b	4.000	291.000	.000
@9.Accordingtoyouhowgraduatescanimprovetheiremployabilityskillst	Pillai's Trace	1.061	21.216	20.000	1176.000	.000
	Wilks' Lambda	.201	30.037	20.000	966.088	.000
	Hotelling's Trace	2.726	39.460	20.000	1158.000	.000
	Roy's Largest Root	2.196	129.104c	5.000	294.000	.000
a. Design: Intercept + @9.Accordingtoyouhowgraduatescanimprovetheiremployabilityskillst						
b. Exact statistic						
c. The statistic is an upper bound on F that yields a lower bound on the significance level.						

Table 12: Multivariate Tests.

Analysis-Based on the above table this can be seen that the value of significance difference is under the standard value of P which is 0.000. The standard P value is 0.05 and

in this case the null hypothesis is true that states that the new way to improve the skills depends on the way to improve the skills.

Tests of, Between-Subjects Effects							
Source	Dependent Variable	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
Corrected Model	10. New Way to improve skills - [Set clear milestones]	414.839 ^a	5	82.968	119.260	.000	
	10. New Way to improve skills - [Better Communication]	319.308 ^b	5	63.862	83.640	.000	
	10. New Way to improve skills - [Self-determination]	361.370 ^c	5	72.274	89.270	.000	
	10. New Way to improve skills - [Plan and prioritize the things]	330.292 ^d	5	66.058	86.142	.000	
Intercept	10. New Way to improve skills - [Set clear milestones]	1358.226	1	1358.226	1952.359	.000	
	10. New Way to improve skills - [Better Communication]	1473.624	1	1473.624	1930.012	.000	
	10. New Way to improve skills - [Self-determination]	1432.940	1	1432.940	1769.906	.000	
	10. New Way to improve skills - [Plan and prioritize the things]	1554.611	1	1554.611	2027.263	.000	
@9.Accordingtoyouhow graduatescanimprovetheiremployabilityskillst	10. New Way to improve skills - [Set clear milestones]	414.839	5	82.968	119.260	.000	
	10. New Way to improve skills - [Better Communication]	319.308	5	63.862	83.640	.000	
	10. New Way to improve skills - [Self-determination]	361.370	5	72.274	89.270	.000	
	10. New Way to improve skills - [Plan and prioritize the things]	330.292	5	66.058	86.142	.000	
Error	10. New Way to improve skills - [Set clear milestones]	204.531	294	.696			
	10. New Way to improve skills - [Better Communication]	224.478	294	.764			
	10. New Way to improve skills - [Self-determination]	238.026	294	.810			
	10. New Way to improve skills - [Plan and prioritize the things]	225.454	294	.767			
Total	10. New Way to improve skills - [Set clear milestones]	2663.000	300				
	10. New Way to improve skills - [Better Communication]	3196.000	300				
	10. New Way to improve skills - [Self-determination]	2957.000	300				
	10. New Way to improve skills - [Plan and prioritize the things]	3414.000	300				
Corrected Total	10. New Way to improve skills - [Set clear milestones]	619.370	299				
	10. New Way to improve skills - [Better Communication]	543.787	299				
	10. New Way to improve skills - [Self-determination]	599.397	299				
	10. New Way to improve skills - [Plan and prioritize the things]	555.747	299				
a. R Squared = .670 (Adjusted R Squared = .664)							
b. R Squared = .587 (Adjusted R Squared = .580)							
c. R Squared = .603 (Adjusted R Squared = .596)							
d. R Squared = .594 (Adjusted R Squared = .587)							

Table 13: Tests of, Between-Subjects Effects.

Based on the above table this can be stated that the average value of R square is around 0.60 that shows there is higher degree of variation in the data that is explained by the independent variable for the dependent variable.

Dependent Variable: 10. New Way to improve skills - [Set clear milestones]

Model: Intercept + @9.Accordingtoyouhowgraduatescanimprovetheiremployabilityskillst

Fig. 4: Set clear milestone to improve skills

Dependent Variable: 10. New Way to improve skills - [Better Communication]

Model: Intercept + @9.Accordingtoyouhowgraduatescanimprovetheiremployabilityskillst

Fig. 5: Better communication to improve skills.

Dependent Variable: 10. New Way to improve skills - [Self determination]

Model: Intercept + @9.Accordingtoyouhowgraduatescanimprovetheiremployabilityskillst

Fig. 6: Self determination to improve skills

Dependent Variable: 10. New Way to improve skills - [Plan and prioritize the things]

Model: Intercept + @9.Accordingtoyouhowgraduatescanimprovetheiremployabilityskillst

Fig. 7: Plan and prioritize the things to improve skills.

VIII. CONCLUSION & SUMMERY

In this research paper research was focusing on the employability skills for students. There are many factors which are responsible for providing employability skills in students. Employers expecting good communication skills, time management skills, leadership skills, problem solving skills critical thinking skills, team work skills and self-management skills from their management students to achieve their organizational goal. With the help of internship program, students can enhance their skills and practice of sharpen up soft skill can be provide so many opportunity to management graduates. Other ways to improve employability skills are completing regularly education courses, seek the trust advice, and take online courses which can improve managerial skills in student. Student should develop their understanding priorities of work that means they need to understand that what task can avoid for few time and what task is need to do on time with the help of this skills student can complete their task on time according to their employer need. With the help of energetic and positive involvement of institution and faculty members, students can get proper direction on the way of skills development.

REFERENCES

- [1.] **Usimasamudrikawaligamage** (2009), Sub Theme A Enhancing Employability through Quality Assurance-ASAIHL 2009. Lecturer, department of Accountancy, University of kelaniya, Shrilanka.
- [2.] NuryakeFajaryati, Budiyo, Muhammad Akhyar and wiranto, (2020), The Employability Skills Need to Face the Demand of Work in the Future: Systematic Literature Reviews. Open Access published by De Gruyter Open Access July 2, 2020.
- [3.] P. Vanitha, Dr. A.T. Jaganatham, A study on Enhancing Employability skills of Graduates in India. International journal of trend in Scientific Research & development, Online – Issn no. 2456-6470, Volume 2, Issue 2.
- [4.] **Nishad Nawaz, Dr. Bal Krishna** (2013). Role of employability skills in Management education: A review. ZENITH International Journal of Business Economics & Management Research, ISSN 2249-8826, ZIJBEMR, Vol. 8, Aug (2013).
- [5.] **Dr. KavitaDesaia, JyotirmayeeRamisettyb, Dr. NiloferHussainic, Dr. MacherlaBhagyalakshmi.** Employability Skills Training Intervention in Higher Education in India: A Model Based Study. Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics education Vol. 12, No. 10, April 2021.